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Abstract:

This deliverable describes the data access plan for Dried Blood Spot Sample (DBSS) data in SHARE. It explains the special character of biomedical data as compared to other survey data and describes the measures that are taken to keep these special data FAIR.

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Executive Summary

This report is Deliverable 5.2 of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, and a result of Task 1 focusing on the legal, ethical and technological issues of access to biomedical data. The aim of the task is to make biomedical data available to the research community via data access that follows the FAIR principles. As an intermediate step to the actual data access, this deliverable provides the data access plan for making biomarker data from dried blood spot samples (DBSS) available. While this deliverable reports on the data access plan for biomarker data collected within the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), the procedure can be informative for other researchers, survey methodologists and data archives who aim on providing biomedical data collected in survey settings.

Objective health data gain importance for researchers who are concerned with population ageing. SHARE therefore includes objective health measures from the beginning. In its sixth wave, SHARE additionally implemented the collection of DBSS as a further innovation. DBSS differ from traditional survey data, as they cannot be released immediately after collection and data cleaning, but they need one further step: laboratory analysis.

The SHARE DBSS are analysed for biomarkers that are associated with age-related health conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, cognitive function, or sarcopenia. While the physical DBSS will not be accessible to external researchers, the obtained blood levels will be published as generated variables alongside the regular SHARE data.

This deliverable encompasses all relevant background information and preparatory steps for making biomarker data accessible following the FAIR principles. It first shortly sums up the implementation of the DBSS collection in SHARE. The FAIR Health principles require specific consideration of data protection and ethical requirements during preparation and implementation of health data collection. It is explained how these principles are met.

DBSS data are not directly comparable to biomarker values obtained from standard samples collected and analysed under routine laboratory conditions. The deliverable describes a structured validation experiment carried out to identify the possible effect of varying fieldwork conditions on the values measured in DBSS. The aim of the experiment was to develop biomarker-specific conversion formulae. They will be used to convert the raw DBSS values into values that are directly comparable to biomarker values obtained from standard blood samples. The conversion of raw DBSS data into easy-to-use standard-equivalents is part of SHARE's approach to make data interoperable and re-usable.

Furthermore, the deliverable includes a description of the DBSS data linkage to the SHARE survey data and gives an overview on how SHARE data in general adhere to the FAIR principles: the data are made "findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable" for a broad researcher community. Regarding user access, the generated variables based on the DBSS data do not differ from the regular SHARE data. They are freely accessible, and the same conditions of use apply.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

BMI	body mass index
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CHARLS	China Health and Retirement Longitudinal <i>Study</i>
DBS	dried blood spot(s)
DBSS	dried blood spot sample(s)
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ELSA	English Longitudinal Study of Ageing
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
HRS	Health and Retirement Study
ID	Identifier
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupations
MPG	Max Planck Society
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
USA	United States of America

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1. Introduction

SHARE, the “Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe”, is a population-based socio-economic survey among people aged 50 plus and with data from 28 European countries and Israel. It investigates individual, economic, health-related, and social impacts of the aging process in order to give answers to the challenges of population aging for individuals and society as a whole. Understanding aging per se and how we age differently given our individual background, current health and socio-economic factors, is the aim of SHARE.

In order to maintain intertemporal, international and intercultural comparability, SHARE has adopted objective data collection in the health domain. From the beginning, SHARE includes physical performance measures such as grip strength, peak expiratory flow, walking speed, and chair stand in the health modules. In 2015, SHARE has collected dried blood spot samples (DBSS) as an additional objective measure of health. Eleven European countries and Israel participated in the DBSS collection.

The motivation to combine biomedical and socio-economic research is manifold: Blood biomarkers e.g., addressing conditions and diseases of older age can help to identify pre-disease physiological processes, which are below the threshold of an individual’s perception. They capture health aspects (yet) unknown to the survey participants, and they can help to understand complex relations between socio-economic conditions, health, cognition, and physiological pathways. Cardiovascular, metabolic, inflammatory, and other biomarkers have been shown to be predictors of mortality and morbidity by themselves or combined with self-assessed health (Gruenewald et al. 2006, Ridker 2007). Furthermore, blood biomarkers shed light on the mechanisms that relate socio-economic factors influenced by lifestyle and environment to morbidity and mortality, which are not confounded by the shortcomings related to self-reported health information.

Collecting blood is the method of choice when combining biomedical and socio-economic research (Williams and McDade 2009). SHARE collected blood using a method particularly adaptable to the circumstances of a very large international population survey. The sampling of dried blood spots (DBS) offers numerous advantages over conventional blood collection (Li and Lee 2014, Li and Tse 2010). DBS are drops of capillary whole blood collected on filter paper from a simple finger prick. The method is regarded less intrusive than venipuncture and easily applied. Blood collected on filter cards can be shipped by regular mail to a laboratory and stored frozen until analyses. This makes DBS samples (DBSS) well suited for many screening programs or population-based studies in the area of public health research.

The analytes, which can be measured in DBSS today, have gradually increased over the years thus making the collection method increasingly interesting. They range from DNA analyses (viral / human) to a variety of proteins, lipids and vitamins (e.g., Brindle, O’Connor, and Garrett 2014, Crimmins et al. 2014, Eyles et al. 2009, McDade, Williams, and Snodgrass 2007, Mei et al. 2001, Skogstrand 2012, Skogstrand et al. 2005) as well as multiple elements helping to identify environmental or workplace-related heavy-metal pollution (Pedersen et al. 2017).

The blood-based biomarkers shall provide SHARE and its users with additional objective health measures to investigate more closely the most common aging-related health conditions in the context of the socio-

economic information gained from its survey. Those health conditions and aging-related diseases include diabetes (e.g., Kalyani, Golden, and Cefalu 2017), cardiovascular disease (e.g. North and Sinclair 2012), decline of kidney function, cognitive decline, but also loss of strength and muscles (sarcopenia).

SHARE collected DBSS from approximately 27,000 respondents in 13 countries, by far the largest sampling of DBSS from a representative adult population.

This report supports researchers, survey methodologists and data archives who intend to make biomedical data available to the scientific community for research purposes. Data providers have to take into account the intrinsic differences of biomedical data collections in comparison to “traditional” self-reported survey data. These data must often be extensively processed, validated and calibrated before they can be made accessible and subsequently analysed with the statistical techniques and models that are common in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). While survey data usually is available directly after the data collection, the inclusion of biological samples into the database requires an additional step: the laboratory analysis of the samples (Schmidutz 2019). This special character of DBSS data requires the review of the general SHARE Data Access Plan and its compliance of the data with FAIR principles, as they are key for establishing open science as good scientific practice in the research community. SSHOC provides manifold tools for the Social Sciences and Humanities to establish FAIR principles in their research and data collections. This report gives an overview on how these principles are met for the DBSS data in SHARE.

2. The SHARE biomarker project

2.1 Dried blood spot samples (DBSS) in SHARE

SHARE implemented the collection of DBSS in 11 European countries and Israel during the main data collection of its sixth wave in 2015. For all participating countries, ethical approvals were obtained from the respective national ethics committees. The approvals require specific information on the entire projects to be given to the participants in order to make their (written) consent be informed. The consent forms and information material state explicitly that participation is voluntary, the results are only used for research purposes (not commercial), and the blood values cannot be linked to the respondents’ identity. Respondents are further informed about data privacy measures, the biomarkers to be analysed in the SHARE DBSS (e.g., most countries excluded DNA analysis now and, in the future, but some allow future analyses for further biomarkers related to the same topics of interest), and storage time of the DBSS (the DBSS from some countries will be destroyed at specific dates). A detailed description of the approval process and country-specific regulations can be found in Schmidutz (2016) and Schmidutz and Weiss (2017). The SSHOC D5.1 provides “Guidelines for ethics considerations in making biomedical survey data FAIR” that should be taken into account when applying for ethics approval.

The fieldwork collection itself including the training of the interviewers was prepared and coordinated centrally to keep all methods, processes, and used materials harmonized across countries (Weiss, Sakshaug, and Börsch-Supan 2018). The DBSS collection took place at the home of the respondents during the regular SHARE

interview. Interviewers were provided with pre-packed collection kits that contained all necessary material to conduct the blood collection. The blood was collected by a simple finger stick; up to five drops were dropped onto a special filter card, let to dry and subsequently sent to a central SHARE biobank located at the Department of Public Health at the University of Southern Denmark in Odense, Denmark. The samples were stored at -23°C at the biobank. For biomarker analysis, part of the contained blood material (small discs punched out of the blood containing filter paper) was subsequently sent to the analyzing laboratories. A description of the entire process from its preparation to sample collection and a summary of the project's success can be found in M. Börsch-Supan et al. (2020).

DBSS have been collected from more than 27,000 respondents (exact numbers per country can be found in MS21 "Protocol of laboratory processing of DBSS data"). Two laboratories, the Staten Serum Institute in Copenhagen, Denmark, and the Department of Laboratory Medicine, University of Washington in Seattle, USA, were entrusted with the DBS analyses. Both laboratories have the expertise to analyze DBS for various blood markers and are able to handle such large amounts of samples. The SHARE DBSS were apportioned amongst the two laboratories into two sets of markers according to the laboratories' expertise in analyzing certain markers. An overview of the derived biomarkers is documented in MS21 "Protocol of laboratory processing of DBSS data".

2.2 Validation

Results from DBS assays cannot be directly compared to the results one would obtain from assays of conventional blood samples using standard laboratory methods (Crimmins et al. 2014, McDade, Williams, and Snodgrass 2007). The DBS values of, e.g., total cholesterol, which is known to be particularly difficult to measure in DBSS, have both a higher mean and a larger variance, influenced by many laboratory and fieldwork-related factors (Thomas et al. 2018, Crimmins et al. 2020, Bowen and Evans 2014).

Recent work has shown that lab-based formulae can be developed and used to transform DBS values into standard-equivalent values. However, they need to address the fieldwork conditions that may affect the quality of DBSS collected for an international survey like SHARE (Weiss and Börsch-Supan 2019, Weiss et al. 2019, Crimmins et al. 2020). SHARE therefore conducted a structured validation experiment simulating fieldwork conditions and sample quality characteristics observed during SHARE fieldwork, namely the size of the DBS, the applied drying time, the outside temperature, total shipment time, and applied humidity protection measures during shipment. DBSS created from venous blood of 20 donors were exposed to varying combinations of these conditions. Additionally, the venous blood of the same donors was analysed using standard methods and capillary DBSS (same as during fieldwork) were created also from the same donors and analysed by the same methods as for the fieldwork samples in SHARE. The results of the experiment can be used to establish field-based conversion formulae for each biomarker in SHARE. These formulae will be used to estimate "standard-equivalent" values from the SHARE DBS values as the listed conditions were all recorded or calculated for all SHARE DBS samples. For this, estimations predict the values that would have been expected if it had been feasible to collect the respondents' venous blood under controlled laboratory settings instead of a DBSS collection during fieldwork (for a detailed description of the validation see A. Börsch-Supan et al. (2020)).

The validation experiment as well as the conversion of the raw DBS values (and the publication of the converted value) is a major contribution to making the DBSS data “re-usable” and “interoperable” in the sense of FAIR principles (see sections 3.2.3 and 3.2.4).

2.3 Linkage of DBSS data to SHARE survey data

DBSS data differ from traditional survey data for several reasons. First – while being collected at the same time and place – there are no “answers” that can be stored digitally and made available together with the regular survey data. Instead, the “outcome” of the DBSS collection is a physical blood sample that has to be stored under appropriate conditions. Second, the blood samples are not the data that will be made available to the research community, but they require one further step: the laboratory analyses of the biomarkers contained in the samples. Only the hereby obtained blood level values are the actual DBSS data that will be published. Last, an identification system is needed to match such data to the corresponding respondent’s survey data. The identification system has to adhere to data privacy regulations, particularly regulations that are in place for sensitive data such as blood parameters (Schmidutz 2016, Schmidutz and Weiss 2017).

SHARE DBSS are linked to the corresponding survey data via a barcode number that is attached to the physical sample as well as entered into the interview instrument by the interviewer. The laboratories list the results of each sample together with the attached barcode number, as well. Hence, the number can be used to link the laboratory results to the traditional survey data without the need or even possibility to identify the respondent. Data cleaning comprises the check of correct linkage by metadata information (the date of the interview and the number of collected blood spots for each sample are noted on the sample card respectively in the interview instrument as well) and the retrieval of initially not matchable samples, e.g., due to typing errors in the barcode number. The data cleaning process has been described in Friedel and Weiss (2017).

SHARE data from each wave are published in multiple modules with each module containing data regarding one topic. The modules are linkable with each other and across waves by a respondent identifier, the “mergeid” which is constant for each respondent over the waves. Some of the modules consist of so-called “generated” variables, i.e. variables that are generated subsequent to the actual data collection. Here, variables from the questionnaire are combined and recoded into substantial constructs from the literature that are then “ready-to-use”. Examples are the BMI score that is calculated from height and weight, the computation of the ISCED coding to measure education, or ISCO for occupation.

The DBSS data will be published in their own generated variables module. The DBSS are currently being analysed for diabetes (HbA1c) and cardiovascular disease risk markers (total cholesterol and high density lipoprotein, triglycerides, C-reactive protein, Cystatin C) and for total haemoglobin indicating anaemia and frailty. These are routine markers and reference values from venous blood samples are well established. Moreover, the samples have been analysed for a more innovative set of markers, namely five cytokine markers, three growth factors (IL-16, IL-8, IL-12/23, IL-18, MCP1; BDNF, VEGF, EGF) and the apolipoproteins ApoE4 and

ApOJ (Clusterin)¹. Given successful validation of the laboratory analyses, the DBSS module will contain the converted values for all biomarkers that are then ready and easy to use for the research community. Whether and how the raw DBS values and other metadata (such as fieldwork conditions, DBSS nonresponse weights) can and will be made available as well, is still subject of discussion. At the time of writing, this list of biomarkers is exhaustive. The analysis of further markers might need additional approval by the national ethic committees; these markers would be restricted to blood parameters related to the same health topic (e.g. cardiovascular diseases or diabetes). In some countries, the analysis of specific other markers has been excluded a priori (e.g. the analysis of DNA).

3. Data access plan confirming FAIR principles

As a guideline for good scientific practice, scientists as well as representatives of the industry, funding agencies and scholarly publishers have developed the FAIR Guiding Principles for the publication of digital resources (Wilkinson et al. 2016, Wilkinson et al. 2018). Following these principles, research data shall be “findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable” to ensure scientific quality and to enhance knowledge and discovery (Wilkinson et al. 2016). It is hoped that the implementation of the FAIR Principles will lead to an improvement in data management and stewardship so that researchers can use existing data to its full potential and thereby thriving scientific innovation.

The FAIR Guidelines have rapidly gained popularity in bio- and natural sciences (van Reisen et al. 2020). However, Mons et al. (2017) criticize that a large share of datasets is still unavailable for reuse. Aiming at providing access to biomarker data to the scientific community, SHARE has a general data access plan for all SHARE data including the biomarker data. As biomarker data are released as a generated variable module as it is common in the SHARE data release, they do not require special qualifications to be used and will be published alongside the regular SHARE data. User access regulations and measures taken to make all SHARE data (including the biomarker data) FAIR are described in this chapter as well as on the SHARE homepage².

3.1 User access regulations and FAIR principles

SHARE has adopted a data release policy that gives free, speedy and convenient access to all scientific users world-wide, fully adhering to the FAIR principles as described in the following sections. There are no costs to data users. All SHARE data are freely available to all scientific users with the only restriction that data users must comply with the SHARE Conditions of Use³ including its ethics and confidentiality rules and the data

¹ The cytokine markers and apolipoproteins are linked to inflammatory processes in the body. They may help to refine risk indicators of cardiovascular disease and/or cognitive decline. Growth factors stimulate cell-type specific growth or differentiation: for example, rising BDNF-levels signal neuronal growth, when the body is active, and are neuro-protective in Alzheimer’s Disease; rising EGF/VEGF marker levels can signal both, tissue healing e.g., of arterial tissue in CVD as well as neoplastic growth in cancer.

² SHARE Data Access: <http://www.share-project.org/data-access.html>; accessed 17.11.2020

³ SHARE Conditions of Use: <http://www.share-project.org/data-access/share-conditions-of-use.html>; accessed 17.11.2020

protection and privacy requirements in accordance with Community and national data protection laws. The data may be used by registered SHARE users only. Access to the data is virtual via the Internet.

Data access will be given via the following procedure⁴:

- *Step 1:* All users are required to register individually with the SHARE Research Data Center and to agree to the user conditions pertaining to the use of the SHARE data. This is a mandatory part of the registration process and is confirmed by the individual user's signature on the "user statement". Non-EU users additionally need to sign the user statement binding them to EU data protection standards. The user first requests access to the data by email, fax, or mail. His/her eligibility for data access has to be declared by means of an affiliation with a scientific institution, such as a university or scientific research institution or a clearly separate and independent research department of a public institution or non-profit organisation. For interested researchers without such an affiliation, access can be granted in justified cases. These users have to provide relevant details about the specific scientific project for which the data shall be used. At this, the scientific character of the project has to be demonstrated in a sufficient manner. The completed and signed user statement is sent to the SHARE Research Data Center.
- *Step 2:* Upon acceptance of the credentials, normally within a few working days, access will be given to the secure SHARE Research Data Centre website via a personal user ID and a password. The individual SHARE user is granted a simple, non-exclusive, non-transferrable right of use of the SHARE data. If access is granted based on a specific scientific project, the right of use is limited to this specific project. The acceptance notification marks the completion of the registration process.
- *Step 3:* The data can then be downloaded by the individual user after successful registration. In each publication using SHARE data the data collection and the main funding institutions have to be acknowledged. In the bibliography of each publication, the used data set(s) have to be cited and users are requested to include the basic literature on SHARE research and methodology in the bibliography. Furthermore, users of SHARE data have to provide references to all forms of publications based on SHARE data to the central SHARE Coordination Team.

3.2 FAIR data principles

3.2.1 Findability

In order to make data findable for both humans and computer systems, data as well as associated metadata should be assigned an abiding, unique identifier and registered in a comprehensible resource (Wilkinson et al. 2016), for example a data archive or institutional repository (Boeckhout, Zielhuis, and Bredenoord 2018).

⁴ All details are available at User Registration: <http://www.share-project.org/data-access/user-registration.html>; accessed 17.11.2020

SHARE uses DOI's to make datasets permanently identifiable and locatable. This will also hold for the DBSS data collected within SHARE. The DOI for all available SHARE data consists of the fixed DOI-prefix (10.6103) and the suffix: /SHARE.w[n].[zzz], whereas n refers to the wave of data collection and zzz to the release number.

SHARE data is registered in the repository of Da|ra, which links every DOI to a set of metadata, a collection of bibliographical and content information, referring to the registered dataset (title, author, publication date, copyright etc.). A DDI based SHARE Data & Documentation Tool is provided to users as a fast, customizable, easy-to-use web interface for browsing and searching the SHARE (meta)data.

To reach out to research communities at the intersection of social and biomedical sciences, metadata references in interdisciplinary repositories will be considered. Not only should SHARE survey users be able to find the SHARE biomarker data, but likewise, biomarker users should be able to find SHARE.

3.2.2 Accessibility

The FAIR Principles state that data should be accessible and retrievable by their identifier using “standardized communications protocol” (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Data and metadata should be stored for the long term and access to metadata should still be available even when the data is not.

Access to SHARE data is provided free of charge to the scientific community after registration. The data is subject to national as well as European Union data protection laws and the conditions of use described in 3.1. SHARE will support users by a website with all public information and by a combination of central and national support points that answer questions and respond to user requests. Users need either Stata or SPSS for data usage. However, users of other statistical software (e.g., R, SAS, or Python) can access the data as well because conversion of datasets between statistical software packages is a standard procedure by now. The data will be deposited at two public data archives:

- The German Data Archive for the Social Sciences, a public data archive run by GESIS in Cologne, Germany, member of the CEESDA consortium and certified during the ESFRI process.
- The CentERdata Archive, located at Tilburg University in Tilburg, Netherlands, certified by the Max Planck Society (MPG) as part of the integration of the SHARE coordination into the MPG.

3.2.3 Interoperability

Since different data often needs to be merged, datasets should be ready to be exchanged, interpreted and combined in a (semi)automated way by humans as well as computer systems. Therefore, to be interoperable, data as well as metadata should be described and structured in a “formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language” (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Using domain-specific standards in structuring data and formatting metadata would facilitate the mining and integration of different data sources (Borgman 2012).

SHARE data is made available to the research community for two of the most common statistical software packages Stata and SPSS. However, users of other statistical software (e.g., R, SAS or Python) can access the data as well because conversion of datasets between statistical software packages is a standard procedure by

now. For example, the open software application R supports packages to read-in Stata and SPSS files, which allow SHARE data to be analyzed with open software as well. Within all these statistical software applications, SHARE data can be combined with other data sources, e.g. regional data, in any format the software supports.

The standards and vocabularies used allow interdisciplinary interoperability. The SHARE (meta)data is comprehensively documented, based on DDI standards, to enable researchers from all disciplines to use it for their research and combine it with other datasets.

Multidisciplinary and cross-nationality belong to the key features of SHARE. SHARE is not only a European project. It is embedded in a network of worldwide ageing surveys like the U.S. Health and Retirement Study (HRS), the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA), the China Health and Retirement Survey (CHARLS), and many other ageing surveys in Asia and Latin America.

3.2.4 Reusability

The reusability of data is an important requirement for the replication and validation of previous research findings as well as for the promotion of scientific knowledge (Deshpande et al. 2019). To enable a broad range of researchers to use the data in the future, the data as well as related metadata has to be sufficiently well-described (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Therefore, standards on how data and metadata should be reported are crucial for their reusability and consequentially for scientific innovation and reproducibility (Sansone et al. 2019). However, the reuse of available data poses the potential risks of incorrect conclusions, errors or bias because external researchers might be less familiar with certain details and limitations of the original study (Boeckhout, Zielhuis, and Bredenoord 2018, Spertus 2012). Consequentially, transparency about (re)used data is necessary on the part of researchers.

SHARE data in general and the SHARE biomarker r data will not be restricted in re-use, except for commercial use. Archiving the data together with a detailed documentation of the (meta)data permits re-use of the data without any time restrictions. Data quality assurance processes of SHARE data are described and published with each wave release in the Methodology Volume Series and the Compliance Profiles by SHARE ERIC⁵. This includes, for instance, reports on fieldwork monitoring, sampling, interviewer training procedures, and innovations such as the implementation of DBSS and accelerometer data. Schmidutz and Weiss (2017) document the legal, ethical and organisational aspects of the the inclusion of DBSS in SHARE.

Data re-use of SHARE data is also increased by providing generated modules (e.g. imputations, aggregation of health data, ISCED-codes), additionally generated datasets (job episodes panel) and a teaching dataset for student training and for researchers who have little experience in quantitative analyses of complex survey data.

As described in section 3.1 of this report, transparency of data re-use is being fostered by the request to all users of SHARE data to provide references to all forms of publications based on SHARE data to the central SHARE Coordination Team.

⁵ SHARE Methodology Volumes and Compliance Profiles can be accessed via the SHARE homepage: <http://www.share-project.org/data-documentation/methodology-volumes.html>; accessed 17.11.2020

3.3 Access to DBSS data

For the collection and publication of health-related or sensitive personal data, the FAIR principles have been supplemented by the FAIR Health Principles (Holub et al. 2018). They state that such data collections should be ethically approved prior to implementation. Furthermore, the FAIR Health Principles emphasize the necessity of developing specific policies and data privacy measures for data collection, storage, and processing. The DBSS data adhere to the FAIR principles as ethical approval was obtained in all participating countries prior to the implementation of the project (see section 2.1) and special measures for data privacy protection were taken, e.g. the linkage of the biomarker values to the interview data via a barcode number. No personal id is stored together with the physical samples (see section 2.3).

Granting access to the original biological material might not be fruitful nor feasible since they cannot be analysed by the common data user (Holub et al. 2018). Additionally, it might not be ethical towards the respondents to make all information contained in biological material freely accessible. While survey data usually is available directly after the data collection (after the necessary subsequent data cleaning and quality checks are carried out), the inclusion of biological samples into the survey dataset requires an additional step: the laboratory analyses of the samples (Schmidutz 2019). The analysis results can then be included as variables, often referred to as biomarkers, into the dataset. These variables can be used in statistical analyses for research on e.g., health and ageing. An overview of the SHARE biomarkers is documented in SSHOC report on project Milestone S21 “Protocol of laboratory processing of DBSS data”.

As described in 2.2, laboratory results from DBSS assays cannot be directly compared to the results one would obtain from standard assays of venous blood draws even if the DBSS have been created under standardized laboratory conditions. Moreover, varying fieldwork conditions and sample quality add further variance to the biomarker levels measured in field-collected DBSS. In order to allow researchers of the SSH community to easily *re-use* the DBSS data and to enhance *interoperability*, it is therefore important to compute a conversion formula, which translates the DBS values obtained under fieldwork conditions into “standard-equivalents”, which will be provided to users (A. Börsch-Supan et al. 2020, Weiss and Börsch-Supan 2019).

Overall, DBSS data differ from traditional survey data in terms of project implementation (as they need ethics approval adhering to the FAIR health Principles), they require specific privacy measures (e.g. written consent), and extensive processing is necessary prior to publication (laboratory analysis and validation). The original samples are not made accessible to data users at all. However, the final variables containing biomarker values do not differ from the regular SHARE data and the same conditions of use apply to their access as well. The easy access ensures *accessibility* in the sense of the FAIR principles.

Because the DBSS data differ such from the other survey data, extensive documentation will be provided to the user including a description of how the converted (“standard-equivalent”) and ready-to-use variables have been generated. Metadata for biomarker data in SHARE will be documented along the regular SHARE data and available in a similar manner in the SHARE Data and Documentation Tool, which strictly follows DDI standards. The documentation will also describe possible metadata such as fieldwork conditions that might be included into the published dataset. This documentation will increase the *interoperability* of the DBSS data. Descriptions

on the implementation and data collection as well as on the validation are already available in M. Börsch-Supan et al. (2020), A. Börsch-Supan et al. (2020), Schmidutz and Weiss (2017), Börsch-Supan, Friedel, and Weiss (2017), Friedel and Weiss (2017).

4. Conclusions

DBSS are a valuable source for health data in the setting of a large survey such as SHARE. However, the data derived from such samples differ from traditional survey data in many ways. First, they need specific consideration of data privacy and ethical requirements. The SHARE DBSS data follow the FAIR Health Principles as the collection obtained ethical approval in all participating countries prior to implementation of the project and specific data protection measures are taken for the physical blood samples. Second, the collected samples themselves are not made accessible to external researchers, but they have to undergo laboratory analyses. Only the derived blood level values are published as biomarker variables. Last, DBSS data need some additional processing in order to adhere to the FAIR principles. The raw measured values are not directly comparable to values measured in standard blood samples (venous blood draws) using standard methods. A validation experiment was used to develop conversion equations that will be used to convert the raw values into standard-equivalents, accounting not only for the different kind of blood sample but also for possible fieldwork conditions. The conversion is part of SHARE's approach to make the data *interoperable* and *re-usable*.

While DBSS data differ from traditional survey in the described ways, they do not differ in terms of user access. They are stored at the same location and are *findable* and *accessible* in the same way. Possibly, they will additionally be registered in interdisciplinary, more biomedical repositories to make them findable for an even wider community. Users can get access and download the DBSS data in the same way and under the same conditions as the regular SHARE data. No extra user statement has to be signed. This easy access to the DBSS data is hoped to increase *re-use* of the data further.

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